

TEACHING CRYPTOLOGY USING THE VISUAL E-LEARNING PROGRAM CRYPTOOL 2

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Abstract: *We introduce the reader to the Cryptool applications family: Cryptool 1, Cryptool 2, JavaCryptool 1.0, and Cryptool-Online. A comparison of the main and unique functionality for these tools is given. The focus is on Cryptool 2, offering powerful, visual approach to understanding and teaching cryptology. Some ideas for engaging assignments for the student's homework projects are also provided.*

Keywords: *Cryptool; Cryptool 2; cryptology; education;*

I. Introduction

Modern cryptology involves a lot of mathematical knowledge ranging from simple concepts such as modular arithmetic, matrices, and Boolean functions to much more complex terms such as elliptic curves, groups, and rings. Most researchers acknowledge the two main tasks in secure communications:

- **Cryptography:** securing the transferred information in a way that only the intended recipient can decipher.
- **Cryptanalysis:** involves evaluating cryptographic algorithms to identify intended or inherited flows.

On the other hand, the restrictions on cryptographically secure functions lead to algorithm implementations that are not easy to understand, especially for college students in the field of informatics and computer science. Therefore, software applications that can facilitate and visualize the teaching of such topics are highly valued.

From simple hash functions and ancient crypto schemes such as Caesar's cipher to current standards such as SHA2, AES, and RSA, the curriculum of the courses in cryptology can be selected with the following goals: to explain the need for

secure communications, how it was achieved through the ages with primitive means, what challenges the 21-st century computing poses to secrecy, and how the putative future sufficiently large quantum computer can be a danger to all currently used public key algorithms. The last statement is due to the famous Shor's quantum algorithm [1] for quickly (in polynomial time) factoring big numbers $n = pq$, where p and q are large primes. Some researchers estimate that using at least 850-digits (in decimal notation) primes in RSA can secure the encrypted data until 2040-s (by Table 3 in [2]). This is a prediction based on the hypothesis that Moore's law (every two years the computing power is doubled) is valid, which in the last decade is considered by many prominent pundits in IT as obsolete and invalid (for example NVidia founder and CEO Jensen Huang). Later on, we'll go over how random prime numbers are generated again in the CrypTool software and see how quickly the process generates primes of different sizes.

II. CrypTool versions

One of the applications that is useful for teaching cryptology is CrypTool (<https://www.cryptool.org/>), and our aim is to introduce its various capabilities and versions, with a focus on the most versatile and most recent CrypTool 2. The first version of CrypTool, now named CrypTool 1 (CT1) after the release of the new CrypTool 2 (CT2). CT1 appeared in 1998, was written in C++, and compiled for the Windows OS. Currently, all versions are open source and the project is hosted, funded and supported by the Research Institute Cyber Defence and Smart Data (CODE) <https://www.unibw.de/code-en>, University of the Bundeswehr Munich. We recommend the reader [3], a nice textbook for cryptology using CT2, and SageMath [4]. SageMath is a modern open-source mathematical software system. For now, let's focus on the CrypTool family.

Currently, the versions of CT are:

- CT1 (last stable release 1.4.42 from December 2021).
- CT2 (release 2.1 from January 2024).

- JavaCrypTool 1.0 (JCT version 1.0.9 from September 2023): Java SWT and Eclipse RCP Support realization of extendable e-learning platform covering cryptography, cryptanalysis and IT security in a modern interface. Versions for Windows, Linux, and macOS are available for download.
- CrypTool-Online (CTO): online version of the most common used algorithms that is suitable when the installation of CT2 or JCT is not possible.

An overview of the number of different functions and capabilities (as well as the unique ones) each product in the CrypTool family offers is given in Table 1. This information differs from the above total of 205 and the reason for this is that we have taken it from the Functions Volume section on the official website [6].

Table 1. Number of functions offered in each product in CT family

	CT1	CT2	JCT	CTO
Total number of functions	113	188	115	42
Unique for this tool	53	128	68	19

All of the features that are available in CT1, CT2, JCT, and CTO add up to 344. Despite the fact that both JCT and CT1 offer over 100 unique functionalities, it is clear from these figures that CT2 offers the most capabilities. This is because the development team chose not to incorporate certain redundant or outdated features that CT1 offers in the sequel. Regarding JCT, the majority of its expanded capability relates to cryptosystems and algorithms that are difficult to visualize or implement in CT2.

III. CrypTool 2 – visualizing cryptography

CrypTool 2 is written in C# and its first version appeared in August of 2014 with the purpose to modernize its predecessor. It's open source (Apache License v2.0) and offers a graphical user interface (GUI) for visual programming (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The GUI for CT2

As of 2024, CT2 offers 205 functions and functionalities (an extension from the 113 in CT1). The total number of functions for each category in CT2 is given in brackets as follows:

1. Classic ciphers (41)
2. Modern ciphers (38):
 - Symmetric (28)
 - Asymmetric (10)
3. Steganography (4)
4. Hash functions (16)
5. Cryptanalysis (35):
 - Specific (22)
 - Generic (13)
6. Protocols (20)
7. Tools (51):
 - Boolean (4)
 - Data flow (8)
 - Data IO (15)
 - Random numbers (3)
 - Codes (7)
 - Misc (14)

The templates in CT2 (currently numbering 277) that offer common cryptographic capabilities in pre-defined scenarios are helpful for the novice user. Available templates range from the very basic Caesar's cipher with three inputs: the plaintext P , the

alphabet A , and the key (from the set $\{1, \dots, |A|-1\}$) and the ciphertext output C , to more complex such as Differential cryptanalysis (DCA) Pathfinder (see [5]) with ten components, including DCA Oracle, key recovery, path visualizer, toy cipher, and more.

For the novice user, CT2 offers the Wizard interface, accessible under the menu `New` \rightarrow `Wizard` (the wand icon). Then it is a matter of selecting your task. For example, if you navigate to `Encryption/Decryption (E/D)` \rightarrow `Modern E/D` \rightarrow `Asymmetric E/D` \rightarrow `RSA` \rightarrow `RSA Key generation`, you are presented with ad-hoc generated public (N, e) and private key (N, d) pairs. Alternatively, you have the option to generate a new project and have the following options (Fig. 2):

Figure 2: The default environment for RSA key generation

1. Enter primes manually (p , q , and e).
2. Enter keys manually (N , e , d).
3. Generate random primes: You can specify the number of bits in the primes or an upper limit. There's an option to generate "safe" primes. The default length of the primes is set to 1024 bits. CT2 cautions you that selecting the "safe" prime

generation option could take a long time. CT2 cautions you that selecting the "safe" prime generation option could take a long time. The settings for the primes range have a default value of 1024 bits.

We give the average time of 10 generations on an 11-th generation Intel i7 processor with 3.4 GHz core speed for different bit ranges, in Table 2. Alas, a bigger bit range like 2048 bits takes, on average, about 25 minutes. Compare this to the average of 7 seconds for 2048 primes with bits, when the "Generate safe primes" option is unchecked.

Table 2. Average time of generation of RSA keypairs with different range in bits by CT2

# bits	256	384	512	640	768	896	1024
Average time in sec	3	23	20	18	33	55	120

The last option offered for "RSA Key Generator" in CT2 is named "Use the keys from an X.509 certificate." In this instance, the environment creates the private triple d , p , and q as well as the public pair N , e , after the user chooses the relevant certificate and inputs the correct password.

Alternatively, you can skip the Wizard and select Home → New → Workspace. This is the environment for more complex tasks or combinations of different crypto-schemes. The "drag and drop" interface is particularly useful and offers visual feedback, such as the red STOP (in case of a mismatch) or the green OK (when the input is the needed format). Pressing the play button initiates the execution of the environment once all the components have been placed on the workspace (Fig. 3). Other than the play functionality in the Execute menu, there is the Stop button, which cancels the execution. If you wish to make any changes to the ongoing project, it is imperative that you remember to hit stop. If you want to remove some of the components from the environment, simply press the red close button. Again, remember to stop the execution so that this button can activate.

Figure 3: The CT2 main environment (using AES cryptosystem template as an example)

The Log tool (on the View menu, next to the stop button) offers errors, warnings, info, and debugs for the current project. Other than the New and Open functionality, the File menu offers also Save or Print.

The next menu is Edit and offers standard operations: undo, redo, cut, copy, paste, and remove. Also, there is the submenu Insert useful for adding an image or text to the project in the case that more visual information is needed.

Some ideas for fun and engaging work for the college students can be the following assignments:

- Using your parent's names as a key input to Playfair cypher, encipher your name and place of birth. Playfair cypher is under Classic ciphers tab.
- Take your picture and using Least significant bit (LSB) steganography hide your secret message into it. You can find LSB in the tab named Steganography.
- Think of a good password (don't use any of your actual passwords) and analyze it using Password strength function under Misc tab.
- Use data inputs: from the camera as a 256-bits secret key, and the microphone as a 64-bit initialization vector for stream cypher ChaCha and encipher your secret message.

In summary, CrypTool2 offers a powerful, visual approach to understanding and teaching cryptography, enabling students to experiment with a variety of cryptographic algorithms and concepts. The software's wide range of functions makes it suitable for beginners and more advanced users alike, fostering a deeper understanding of cryptography's practical applications and the potential future challenges posed by emerging technologies like quantum computing.

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